

DECOMPOSING THE GEOMAGNETIC FIELD BY MEANS OF EMPIRICAL ORTHOGONAL FUNCTIONS

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Introduction

The geomagnetic field has been highly studied starting from the first measurements and scientific papers to the present monitoring with the help of satellites. Various methods are used in order to study the characteristics of the geomagnetic field, namely fast Fourier transform (Currie, 1973; Langel et al., 1986), wavelet analysis (Alexandrescu et al., 1995 and 1996; Chambodut and Manda, 2005; Duka et al., 2012), empirical mode decomposition (Roberts et al., 2007; Jackson and Mound, 2010; Buffet et al., 2009).

In this paper the vertical and horizontal components of the geomagnetic field at Earth's surface were decomposed at various timescales using Empirical orthogonal functions and the Hodrick-Prescott filter.

Data and method

The COV-OBS.x1 (Gillet et al., 2015) main geomagnetic field model, covering the time span 1840–2020, was used to obtain time series of the vertical component (Z) and of the horizontal component (H) at the Earth's surface in a $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ latitude/longitude grid. The code and coefficients of the model are available online at <http://www.spacecenter.dk/files/magnetic-models/COV-OBSx1/>.

Two methods were used in order to decompose the geomagnetic field, namely empirical orthogonal functions (EOF) and the Hodrick–Prescott (HP) filter (Hodrick and Prescott, 1997). On short, EOF allows defining the spatial distribution of the oscillation modes, their temporal variation as well as their relevance in terms of variance (Bjornsson and Venegas, 1997). Bjornsson and Venegas (1997) were the first to discuss the confusion in the literature between the Empirical orthogonal functions (EOF) and the Principal component analysis (PCA) as both terms were used to describe the same method. The authors proposed that the term EOF to be used to describe the spatial distribution of the variability modes and the PC term to be used for the temporal variation of the variability modes. The principle of the HP filter is that a time series is the sum of a long term component (trend) and a cyclic component. The determination of the long term component is equivalent to a cubic spline smoother.

Results

The Z and H time series, in a $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ global grid, obtained using the COV-OBS.x1 model were decomposed in oscillation modes using the EOF method as well into a long term and a cyclic component by means of HP filtering. The long term component resulted using the HP filter, with amplitudes reaching 7000 nT (vertical component), is associated to the internal field while the cyclic component, with much smaller amplitudes, could correspond to the external field. Further the long term component is filtered by means of a Butterworth filter (1930) with different cut-off periods in order to obtain oscillation at inter-centennial (> 100 years) and sub-centennial (60-90 years) timescales.

The EOF analysis shows that the first three oscillation modes are characterized by periodicities of >100 years and describe 75.83% (mode 1), 13.29% (mode 2) and 4.92% (mode 3), in case of Z, respectively 77.28% (mode 1), 9.46% (mode 2) and 5.74% (mode 3), in case of H, of the characteristics of the geomagnetic field. EOF modes 4 and 5 are characterized by dominant periodicities of 70-90 year. These modes are responsible for 2.91% (mode 4) and 1.86% (mode 5) of the vertical component characteristics, respectively 3.67% (mode 4) and 2.22% (mode 5) of the H characteristics. Although the variance of the modes 4 and 5 is rather small compared to that of the first three modes, these two modes are responsible for the detailed structure of the geomagnetic field. Modes 6-10 that have a total variance of 1.18% (Z) and 1.63% (H) also lend to the detailed structure of the geomagnetic field.

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